

Evaluation of ESOPs as a reward management practice in the Indian IT industry

Dr. Atul Kumar¹, Dr. S. G. Walke², Dr. Mahavir M. Shetiya³

¹Associate Professor, Siddhant Institute of Business Management, Pune, Maharashtra, India

²Professor, S.N.G. Institute of Management and Research Pune, Maharashtra, India

³Associate Professor, S.N.G. Institute of Management and Research, Pune, Maharashtra, India

ABSTRACT

Employee Stock Option Schemes ("ESOPs") quite unheard in India are now gaining popularity significantly, particularly during the previous few years. Confronted with the issue of poaching and brain drain, the software industry particularly has understood the significance of employee stock options to recruit and retain the best employees. In fact, new vistas in this field have opened up, parent organizations particularly those situated in the United States have discovered employee stock options a helpful human resource development tool. Cross border stock alternative plans, whereby Indian occupant employees, take an interest in global stock alternative plans of their parent company (or any foreign company of a similar group) are presently stylish. This study looks into the effectiveness of ESOPs as a reward management practice in the Indian IT industry. 100 IT employees spread all over the country were sampled for this purpose by way of a small survey. Their opinion was taken to check if ESOPs have been effective or not. Employees widely agreed that ESOPs have been highly effective as a reward management practice. Other industries can also adopt ESOPs as an effective reward management practice.

Keywords: Reward Management, Employee Retention, Employee Stock Options Plan, IT industry

1. INTRODUCTION

The idea of ESOP itself has an old history going back 2000 years to Arthashastra. Chanakya, the creator setting out the standards for compensating cowherds characterized the groups into three classifications alongside three unmistakable remuneration structures. For the super variety of cows, a fixed pay was recommended to guarantee that the crowd was not over abused for momentary additions. For the mediocre variety, a fixed return was given to the proprietor and any abundance over that was paid to the cowherd as it was credited to their endeavors. Going to the second rate breeds, the whole pay was shared between the proprietor and the cowherd as the job of the cowherd was basic.

The rationale underlying the compensation structure was to relate the returns/income to the asset quality and the role played by the employee in generating returns. Where the benefit assumed a key job in deciding the arrival, employees got a fixed offer as their commitment was just an empowering influence, then again where the advantage quality was essential and the employees had a generous job in upgrading the quantum of profits created, the employees got a variable as well as a significant share of the return.

In present times, the connection between individual contribution and participation in ownership of the assets is widely noticeable in technology firms, where ESOPs are progressively articulated in one of the three circumstances: businesses in their initial phase, at senior management levels in bigger organizations and at long last in business segments where individual contribution is the difference between success and failure, as in product organizations in the tech space.

ESOPs in India

Though not very well publicized, Wipro if not one of the earliest companies in India, was the first Indian company in 1985, to introduce ESOPs. However, it was Infosys in the 1990s that brought ESOPs into public discourse with a large number of ESOP rupee millionaires and billionaires that it created.

In 1990s, ESOPs became more glittering and attractive as Income tax was a critical factor. Being exempt from tax at the time of exercise of the options and also at the time of sale due to the then prevailing tax laws, the value of ESOPs got

doubled compared to its alternative salaries. Notwithstanding the fact that this ‘loophole’ was plugged in early 2000’s, ESOPs continued to be attractive, as the employees got the benefit of stock ownership in their organization without making any upfront investments.

After the telecom and dotcom bubble burst in early 2000’s, ESOPs came under great scrutiny resulting in the need to duly account for the cost of ESOPs in the accounting books by the issuing companies. Earlier, ESOPs were taken as free and companies issuing them were not required to book the cost of options if the exercise price was at par with the market value. With the accounting change that called for the cost of ESOPs to be accounted, well-established and profitable companies did not see much benefit in issuing ESOPs. However, in the start-up world ESOP has retained its preeminent position and looks well destined for the future.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

As indicated by Employee Ownership Foundation (2016), it helps upgrade the levels of intensity, improves efficiency and lifts the arrangement of free endeavors in US. Employee Stock Option Plans means to align singular interests with the authoritative (McHugh et al, 2005). ESOPs are basic to the greater part of the associations that are claimed by employees (Knapp, 1988). Employee Stock Option Plans were a generally new section however keeps on being famous around the world. Their utility in improving individual and hierarchical execution has been completely discussed and distinctively replied. Other than the above it can get inspiration and maintenance and fill in as commitments to the employees and help in management of individuals (Martin et al., 2016).

As a matter of fact, the beneficial outcome of ESOs are dictated by their capability to inspire (Torp, 2011) as it is one of the parts that rouses employees for harder work (Blasi et al., 2008). They are a piece of a few significant issues that contemporary associations experience in employee management (Martin et al., 2016) and are a piece of guard systems utilized by associations (Dann and DeAngelo, 1988). Also it adds to the key an incentive just as human capital uniqueness (Lepak and Snell, 2002) makes impacts for riches that are certain in nature (Dhillon and Ramirez; 1994) and helps in keeping up great employee relations (Leat, 2009). They additionally help in evading takeovers by setting stocks with confided in employees, have low levels of hazard the odds of takeover (Beatty, 1995). ESOPs have been emphatically engendered as a positive HR practice in various models proposed {(Martin et al., 2016); (Ledford, 2014); (Bloom and Van Reenen, 2011); (Barringer et al., 2005); (Poutsma et al, 2015)}. They have helped in the endurance of associations and ESOs have helped them in their accomplishment in intense occasions (Gilbert et al, 2009).

Most of the studies have been carried in non-Indian contexts. Hence this study, that undertakes an assessment of the effectiveness of ESOPs in the Indian IT industry.

3. METHODS

Following methodology was designed for the study to collect primary data.

- a. Select using random sampling 100 IT employees from different part of the country
- b. Design and validate a 10-point each questionnaire for ascertaining effectiveness of ESOP
- c. Seek responses on a 5-point agree-disagree scale
- d. Conduct the survey
- e. Summarize the responses
- f. Compare the aggregate agree/disagree percentage of the 100 respondents for the 10 questions with a hypothesized mean of the population at 50% agreement/disagreement (taking it as a matter of chance)
- g. Apply a t-test at 95% confidence level
- h. Analyze the results

The hypotheses set in this regard were as under –

- Ho – ESOPs have not been effective in India as an element of reward management practice
- Ha – ESOPs have been effective in India as an element of reward management practice

The study was conducted across India. The 10 questions asked to respondents for assessment of effectiveness were as under –

Table 1: The 10 questions asked to respondents for assessment of effectiveness

Sr. No	Question
1	Do you agree ESOPs have an impact on attrition rates?
2	Do you think that this factor is a "motivation" factor (and not a "hygiene" factor)?
3	Do you think that your Companies strategy related with this factor is at par with local peer companies?
4	Do you think that your Companies strategy related with this factor is at par with global standards?
5	According to you does the Companies strategy on this aspect has been flexible enough to adjust to changing environment?
6	Do you believe that the company has been innovative on this aspect?
7	Do you believe that the company had a strategic focus in this area?
8	Do you agree that ESOPs give a sense of ownership to employees?
9	Is the ESOP flexible enough to enable you to liquidate holdings when markets are doing well?
10	Do you agree that ESOPs are a success notwithstanding stock market volatility?

Scheme formed for testing of hypotheses

- Responses would be collected under 2 sections (prospects and problems) of the questionnaire on a 5-point agree-disagree scale,
- The responses under each of the sections would be aggregated under two groups of agree and disagree,
- While doing so for each of the extreme responses, a weight of 2 would be so as to distinguish them from the non-extreme responses,
- For each of the question an average count will be calculated in the two opposites,
- Percentages to questions under a particular section of the questionnaire will be averaged to get a single score for that section,
- The section-wise average score percentage will be compared with a hypothesized mean of the population of 50% score connoting an event by chance and not due to statistical significance,
- P-values will be calculated and the null hypotheses will be checked for rejection or non-rejection. These calculations would be done at 95% confidence level using a t-test since standard deviation (SD) of the population is not known.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

- Descriptive analysis of the sample (Table set 2)**

Domicile of respondents

Sr. No.	Area	Number of respondents-IT employees	Percentage
1	Mumbai	8	8%
2	Pune	14	14%
3	Chennai	20	20%
4	Delhi	15	15%
5	Hyderabad	1	1%
6	Kolkatta	10	10%
7	Bengaluru	7	7%
8	Kolkatta	4	4%
9	Chandigarh	6	6%
10	Others	15	15%
	Total	100	100%

Gender

Sr. No.	Gender	Number of respondents-IT employees	Percentage
1	Male	52	52%
2	Female	48	48%

	Total	100	100%
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Age

Sr. No.	Age-group	Number of respondents-IT employees	Percentage
1	20-29 years	21	21%
2	30-39 years	46	46%
3	40-49 years	25	25%
4	>=50 years	8	8%
	Total	100	100%

Type of IT Company

Sr. No.	Type	Number of respondents-IT employees	Percentage
1	Software	72	72%
2	Hardware	25	25%
3	Mix	3	3%
	Total	100	100%

Work Experience

Sr. No.	Experience	Number of respondents-IT employees	Percentage
1	< 5 years	12	12%
2	5-10 years	26	26%
3	>10 years	62	62%
	Total	100	100%

Inferential analysis

Agreement Percentages for questions

Sr. No.	Prospects	Agree %
1	Do you agree ESOPs have an impact on attrition rates?	85%
2	Do you think that this factor is a "motivation" factor (and not a "hygiene" factor)?	89%
3	Do you think that your Companies strategy related with this factor is at par with local peer companies?	80%
4	Do you think that your Companies strategy related with this factor is at par with global standards?	85%
5	According to you does the Companies strategy on this aspect has been flexible enough to adjust to changing environment?	90%
6	Do you believe that the company has been innovative on this aspect?	87%
7	Do you believe that the company had a strategic focus in this area?	84%
8	Do you agree that ESOPs give a sense of ownership to employees?	82%
9	Is the ESOP flexible enough to enable you to liquidate holdings when markets are doing well?	86%
10	Do you agree that ESOPs are a success not withstanding stock market volatility?	87%
	Average	86%
	SD (Standard Deviation)	0.03028
	H1 (Hypothesized Mean)	50%
	Ho (Sample Mean)	0.86
	n (Sample size)	100
	t-value	117.25
	p-value	0.0000

Given the p-value of <0.0001 the null hypothesis that the ESOPs have not been effective as an element of reward management practices in the Indian IT industry stands rejected.

DISCUSSION

The overall average agreement of the respondents for the effectiveness of ESOPs in IT industry in India was 86%. The maximum agreement 93% was recorded for the factor flexibility while the minimum agreement 80% was recorded for the question of your Companies strategy related with this factor is at par with local peer companies. The standard deviation of the agreement percentages for the 10 questions was 0.03. Thus, there was an overwhelming agreement in favor of the 10 identified factors for the effectiveness of ESOPs in IT industry in India.

CONCLUSION

There is an overwhelming agreement among the IT sector employees that ESOPs have clicked as an effective reward management practice. A wide range of factors have been responsible for this effectiveness including flexibility, innovativeness, being strategic in nature etc. It is heartening to note that ESOPs have been rated strongly as a “motivational” factor and not as a “hygiene” factor. Thus, beyond any doubt ESOPs have been a great model of rewarding employees with a sense of ownership along with significant monetary gains. The story of the driver of Narayan Murthy of Infosys becoming a millionaire is very famous. This is the story of ESOPs in the Indian IT companies. Employees are sensitive to rewards and they give their best when they are attracted with glittering rewards. ESOPs, is one of them. And it is there to stay for at least some time in the Indian IT sector.

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